

Social Services Provided to Patients Attending Primary Health Care Centers, Riyadh Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

Introduction: Social Services is an essential part of the PHC procedures. This work prescribes the diversity of services supplied to support quality in health care services at PHC, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.

Methods: The study comprised patients who got social services from the social services overflow unit at PHC in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. Frequency distribution patient and par shard altered to describe the study population, and par shard produced to explain details of services provided.

Results: The social services unit served 411 patients, with 60% married and 80% widowed, 17% illiterate, and 66% had a housing adaptation for the sick and his family. 46.22% average, family support 40.14% good, and connection with the surrounding environment 42.10%, Social Services' Health Status 51.6% chronic sickness and 49.% anxiety, 67% low income, treatment recommendations for social services. Financial aid was provided to 53.5% of patients, 68.6% for procedures, and 31% for other services such as guidance and support.

Conclusion: The social service program in PHC is an essential component of primary health care services. It promotes quality improvement in healthcare services. Social services can improve the quality of health care services provided in primary health care. And the same time helping patients to get improved access to health care services through counseling and financial aid. Social services also have a role in improving the awareness of family members of patients' conditions and determinants. Social services in PHCs realize the social responsibility of primary health care services towards the families of patients in the community.

Introduction

In August 2020, a cross-sectional data collection from a June 2016 survey in Ontario was analyzed. As a result, he noted that most practices (84.2%) included a social worker, however, some also had other mental health practitioners. In almost every practice having social workers, they (including individuals classified as mental healthcare practitioners) were active in practice-level efforts to support mental health delivery. Several practices provided care that went beyond mental healthcare, ranging from preventive and health promotion (64.5%) to palliative care (16.8%) [1]. In

certain practices, staff provided group visits for healthy behavior (43.6%) and self-management (~33%). Surprisingly, the roles of social workers in practices where they were the sole authorized mental health providers were not significantly different from those in practices with other mental health practitioners on staff. A July 2018 study discovered that having a social support network could improve one's resilience, quality of life, ability to adapt to tough circumstances, and ability to mobilize resources in the face of illness-causing events [2]. All of these variables can help to improve your physical, mental, and psychological wellness. A cross-sectional study of 1,466 patients

More Information

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aged 18-65 at primary care facilities in Rio de Janeiro and São Paulo investigated the link between physical ailments, common mental disorders, and social support networks. We used the Social Network Index (SNI) to evaluate the support network in terms of isolation and integration. The doctor/nurse filled out the questionnaire to assess the physical disease diagnosis, and the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale was utilized to diagnose mental diseases. We discovered that the pattern of social assistance varied depending on the prevalence of physical or mental illnesses. Diabetes and isolation were found to have negative connections, as did integration, anxiety, and depression. Positive relationships were found between isolation and anxiety, as well as isolation and depression [3].

Background for August 2021. Growing demand from an aging population with many conditions has resulted in complicated health and social care demands that necessitate services that are more integrated. Integrating primary care and social services might help better use resources while improving patient, family, and caregiver experiences. There is little information on progress, particularly significant impediments and drivers of integration, to influence large-scale national reform.

He claimed that thirty-seven interviews had been performed across England with GPs, nurses, social care personnel, commissioners, local government officials, volunteer and private sector workers, patients, and car suppliers. Groups of like-minded people, supported by strong leadership, increased interface roles to bridge system gaps, and service co-location were all factors driving integration. Barriers included professional and Trans-disciplinary tensions, organizational self-interest, and record-sharing issues.

He concluded that the same motives and challenges to integration identified in other contexts exist in primary care and social services. The benefits of integration are unlikely to be achieved unless they are included in the design and implementation of new projects. Efforts should extend beyond local and professional changes to incorporate broader system and policy-level efforts. This will encourage a more system-wide approach to integrated care reform, which is required to satisfy the complex and rising requirements of an aging multimorbid population [4].

On November 10, 2023, the social work profession was gaining popularity, focusing on assisting individuals in addressing their needs to enhance their social, emotional, and physical health. Even while early health-focused social workers primarily served hospitals, they understood the importance of social variables in their attempts to enhance the health of people and communities as a whole. He also discussed the hunt for the requirements that social service providers must

meet, the useful functions they perform, and the rules that govern their profession.

Consequently, he disclosed that the Bureau of Labor Statistics (BLS) projects that employment growth for social workers specializing in health care will reach 11% between 2021 and 2031, more than double the average growth rate for all occupations. The organization projects that an additional 20,000 healthcare social workers will be required during that time. Because of the aging population of the nation, new medications and medical treatments will be required, and social services providers will be needed to assist senior citizens and their families in adjusting to these changes [5].

On October 16, 2023, social workers in healthcare serve as advocates for patients and family members who disagree with the possibilities for their treatment. For example, healthcare social workers may help with appeals for Medicare beneficiaries who believe they have been discharged early. The trust established between social workers and patients is crucial in this advocacy position.

Their role revolves around:

- Screening and evaluating patients and families.
- Performing psychosocial assessments of patients
- Guiding patients and families in understanding the illnesses, conditions, and treatment options
- Helping patients and families transition into a hospital stay or a new department of the hospital.
- Educating patients and families on the roles of healthcare team members, levels of health care, rights, and resources [6].

Healthcare Policy Politiques de Sante:

This article, which was published in August 2020, aims to investigate the continuity and accessibility of French-language healthcare and social services in the Champlain region of Ontario. It does this by utilizing an analytical framework that integrates the linguistic aspect of care, caregivers, and those in need of care into a system of health and social services that is surrounded by political, organizational, social, and community structures.

In this, he documented the experiences of French-speaking elders seeking treatment, as well as those of health and social service providers and managers. Trajectories through the system were described using data from two qualitative exploratory investigations.

As a result, he observed that participants demonstrated how, in addition to community vitality, difficulties within each of the system's symbolic, political, or regulatory and organizational structures influence these trajectories.

To fulfill the requirements of francophone elders, he found that more effort that was needed to improve the coordination of French-language services within the organizational, regulatory, and policy structures [7]. Arabic countries, such as Sudan, have made significant efforts to support social services in health care. Social service is an ancient humanitarian profession that arose due to various factors, including the Industrial Revolution and World Wars.

Because of the social service responses to these various conflict-related problems, those societies were left with poverty, widowhood of women, many orphans, population migration from the countryside to cities, and the emergence of economic, social, and political problems.

Because of the variety of problems, that social service faced at the time, particularly in the fields of family, childhood, the elderly, the infirm, and factory workers, it evolved into a renewed, changing, and advanced profession that continues to keep up with economic, social, and political changes today.

Medical social service has entered Sudan since the 1960s through the embrace of psychology, that is, psychiatric clinics and hospitals, at the hands of Dr. Taha Bashir, who noticed that the majority of diseases that patients complain of and that come to the hospital are mostly due to the social worker, especially when they return to the hospital. In their surroundings, individuals confront the challenge of stigma from members of society, particularly people with psychological and mental problems. This demanded the involvement of social workers, who were responsible for creating awareness about the nature of these disorders and the relevance of society in assisting patients in overcoming their issues and recovering.

Because of the above, we observe that there are various obstacles facing the growth of medical social services in Sudan, which undermines its position in society, especially in the medical profession, for the following reasons: A professional dimension represented by the incompetence and qualification of social workers and their insufficient professional preparation.

1. A societal factor comes from the lack of acknowledgment of social workers due to a lack of understanding of the importance of social services and their role in the medical profession, among other elements.

2. An administrative dimension that is indicated by other teams of doctors and psychologists' refusal to collaborate with the social worker in collaborative work and their treatment of him as inferior.

3. The practice of the profession by anyone other than social workers.

4. An institutional dimension is that the institution does not give adequate resources to the social worker to assist him in resolving clients' issues. It is imperative that social workers have professional preparation, as well as technical skills and procedures, to enable them to perform their duties with efficacy and efficiency across the board.

The social worker must demonstrate his value in different institutions by understanding his responsibilities and using the required abilities.

Social workers need to stay up to date with advancements and modifications in their field as well as in other disciplines that study human behavior and other social structures [7].

Furthermore, in Jordan, social workers carry out the following duties: * Leading social studies for patients who recommended by medical professionals.

- Providing support to the patient or those caring for him in managing and facilitating administrative procedures, such as the issuance of medical reports, companion cards, and anything pertaining to accounting transaction procedures.

- Scheduling family therapy sessions or individual counseling sessions for the patient to aid in their adaptation.

Providing various recreational and educational services for children, and coordinating with many institutions that care for children to hold periodic recreational parties in order to help alleviate the psychological pressures that are often associated with physical injuries and chronic diseases.

Services provided:

- Assessing patients using social studies
- Family and individual therapy sessions regarding the effects of the disease on the patient's life in many aspects, as well as training and certifying family support parties and fostering increased communication
- locating the sufferer a qualified substitute following his recuperation
- overseeing the education of trainees affiliated with Jordanian universities

- As part of the rehabilitation program, field visits will made to assess the housing situation, the surroundings, and the preparedness of the family to accept and manage the patient's health condition.

- Collaboration with government agencies, neighborhood organizations, and organizations that support military patients and their families

- In order to provide the patient with financial and religious assistance, get in touch and work together with military groups and institutes [9].

Social workers in Saudi Arabia work extremely hard in the healthcare industry. One of their main goals is to assist patients in overcoming social and psychological obstacles that can prevent them from benefiting from their treatment plan.

Enabling people to access social services through the community's resources.

It helps spread knowledge about illnesses and ways to avoid them.

University students studying social services are well-trained and certified, which helps to highlight and enhance their abilities.

Responsibilities of the medical social worker:

1. Providing patients and their families with social and psychological assistance through

- Examine the political, social, and financial landscape.
- Delivering social and psychological counseling
- Assisting patients in choosing the right course of action for their problems
- Aiding in the reduction of the impacts of trauma or unpleasant feelings for patients and their families.
- Supplying patients with the information they want and responding to their queries.

2. Guiding patients to other community organizations so they may take advantage of their offerings, like:

3. Monitor the health status of individuals with long-term illnesses [10]. Furthermore, in Bahrain working in tandem with the medical team's specialists to provide the best possible care for patients.

Supplying patients and their families with emotional and psychological support as well as problem-solving via the use of neighborhood resources.

Assisting long-term patients with their discharge when all of their requirements for medical care and social assistance have been satisfied.

Increasing social consciousness by offering patients and their families information and counseling.

Coordinating plans and activities with the Ministry of Health's social service divisions to improve communication and deliver the best possible services.

Working to teach university students seconded by universities and institutions, as well as to enlighten them about the function of social researchers in the medical complex.

Participation in social activities and programs organized by commercial and public entities.

Participating in local and international conferences, seminars, and lectures. The department helps and assists the patient by communicating with various "private and governmental institutions" based on the needs of the case in order to achieve the objective of social intervention [11].

Local perspectives

The Saudi government is concerned about residents' health since they are the most important pillar of progress.

Our objective is to drive progress in primary health care via excellence in patient care, education, research, and

community services, as well as to satisfy the Saudi Kingdom's 2030 healthcare vision.

Furthermore, the mission is to provide accessibility, continuing comprehensive, safe, effective, and compassionate family-centered care, practice evidence-based healthcare, enhance health promotion, embrace social and cultural needs, value scholarly activity, enrich working and learning environments, support teamwork, and constantly striving to improve our services. We are committed to improving health and disease prevention in the communities we serve.

The roles and responsibilities of the social worker in the hospital:

1. Investigating patient cases, beginning with contacting their families to get basic information about the patient's life, stages, and socialization that influence his sickness.
2. Helping the patient accept the disease. Acceptance entails not only accepting the reality of the sickness, but also educating the patient about the nature of his disease and including him in the treatment plan.
3. Conduct interviews and deliver information to patients' family.

Methods

A descriptive analysis of social service initiatives in primary health care settings. Describe the attitudes and responses of patients to the social services offered.

The study comprised patients who got social services from the social services overflow unit at PHC in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. Frequency destroy patient and par shard had altered to characterize the research population, while par shard had created to highlight the specifics of the services offered.

Cross-sectional research comprised 411 social service patients.

Results

Description of Social Service Patients at PHC, Riyadh

Table 1: Marital Status for Social Services Patients at PHC-PSMMC

Marital Status	Number	%
Child	13	3.1%
Single	35	8.5%
Married	251	61%
Widow	77	18.7%
Divorced	20	4.8%
Separated	15	3.6%
Total	411	

Figure 1: Frequency Distribution of Marital Status of Social Services Patients

Table 2: Education Level for Social Services Patients at PHC-PSMMC

Level of Education	Number	%
Illiterate	71	17%
Read and Write	77	18.7%
Primary	88	21.4%
Secondary	54	13%
High	57	13.8%
Diploma	28	6.8%
Universal	36	8.7%
Total	411	

Figure 2: Frequency Distribution of Educational Level of Social Services Patients, the Highest Percentage of Primary School Certificates is that Most of the Social Service Beneficiaries are from the Elderly Category

Table 3: Style of Home Patient Live in for Social Services at PHC -PSMMC

Style of home patient lives in	Number	%
Villa	30	7.2%
Flat	155	37.7%
Apartment	184	44.7%
Traditional Arabic House	42	10.2%
Total	411	

Figure 3: Frequency Distribution of Style of Home Patient Lives in of Social Services Patients the Highest Percentage Lived in Apartments, Followed by Flat

Table 4: Housing Patient for Social Services at PHC-Patient

Type of residence	Number	%
Owned	275	66.9%
Rent	136	33%
Total	411	

Figure 4: Frequency Distribution of Housing Ownership of Social Services Patients for Owned

Table 5: Asses the Social Services for Patient PHC-PSMMC

Asses the social and family situation		
The degree of adaptation of the patient with his family	Number	%
Low	46	11.20%
Average	190	46.22%
Good	152	36.98%
High	23	5.60%
total	411	100%
The level of the family support	Number	%
Low	53	12.90%
Average	155	37.71%
Good	165	40.14%
High	38	9.24%
total	411	100%
The degree of interaction with the urrounding environment	Number	%
Low	53	12.90%
Average	173	42.10%
Good	125	30.41%
High	60	14%
total	411	

Figure 5: Frequency Distribution of Adapting with Family the (Average) Percentage of the Patient's Adaptation to His Family was Highest

Figure 6: Frequency Distribution of Family Bonding The Highest Percentage of (Good) was in the Level of Support and Family Cohesi

Figure 7: Frequency Distribution of Family The Highest Percentage of Interaction with the Surrounding Environment among Social Service Patients was (Average) because of Advanced Age and the Psychological Effects of Chronic Diseases

Table 6: Health Status for Social Services Patient PHC- PSMMC

Health status	Number	%
Chronic diseases	345	51.6%
Liver disease	25	3.7%
Heart patent	52	7.7%
Other	246	36.8%
total	668	

Figure 8: Frequency Distribution of Health Status of Social Services Patients, Chronic Diseases had the Highest Percentage, Followed by Other Diseases such as Bone and Digestive System Diseases

Figure 10: Frequency Distribution of the Social Problem of Social Service Patient was Limited Income. Followed by the Problem (Uneducated)

Table 7: The Social Effects of the Disease Social Services Patient PHC- PSMMC

The Social Effects of the disease	Number	%
Depression	165	27%
Anxiety	300	49.6%
Divorce	14	2.3%
No work	125	20.6%
total	604	

Figure 9: Frequency Distribution of the Social Effects of the Disease Social Services Patients, the Highest Percentage of Anxiety and Stress, Often Accompanied by Depression, was the Next Highest Percentage

Table 8: The Social Problem for Social Services for Patient at PHC- PSMMC

The Social Problem	Number	%
Uneducated	114	24%
Limited income	315	67%
Addiction	8	1.7%
Domestic Violence	31	6.6%
total	468	

Table9: Treatment Recommendations for Social Services Patient at PCH -PSMMC

Treatment Recommendation	Number	%
Provision of guidance	291	46%
Financial aid	335	53.5%
Total	626	

Figure 11: Frequency Distribution of Treatment Recommendations of Social Services Patients, Financial Support has the Highest Percentage, Followed by Guidance and Moral Support

Table10: Procedures Taken for Social Services Patient at PHC –PSMMC

Procedures Taken	Number	%
Financial aid	311	68.6%
Airline Ticket	0	0
Accommodation	1	0.22%
Other	141	31%
total	453	

Figure 12: Frequency Distribution of Procedures Taken of Social Services Patients, the Highest Percentage was for Financial Aid, Followed by Others such as Providing Moral Support and Social Counselling

Figure 13: Questionnaire on Patients Satisfaction with Social Services in Primary Health Care

The questionnaire revealed the following results:

- Very agree : 19%
- Agree : 38.6%
- Neutral : 22.9%
- Disagree : 12.5%
- Strongly disagree : 6.6%

Discussion

Kirstein Rummery divided Anna Coleman's primary study into two pieces in 2002. The first is a longitudinal study that uses structured interviews with key stakeholders to trace the growth of a nationally representative sample of 15% of English PCG/Ts throughout the first three years of their existence (Wilkin, Gillam, & Coleman, 2001; Wilkin, Gillam, & Leese, 1999). The second portion utilizes the yearly

survey as a sample frame to identify four PCG/Ts, and an in-depth qualitative examination of partnerships operating at the strategic, managerial, and operational levels.

Primary health care in the United Kingdom has seen considerable organizational upheaval, which would ordinarily make it difficult to maintain and create collaborations with external groups (Hiscock & Pearson, 1999; Regen, Smith, & Shapiro, 1999). However, the data from this study suggests that considerable progress had been made toward partnership functioning, while there is still a long way to go before primary health and social care in the UK are fully integrated.

Our efforts are on par with, if not better than, those of international and Arab countries. We advocate equity and accessibility while delivering basic healthcare services.

Conclusion

From our work presented here, we see that social services in primary health care in Saudi Arabia have an important role. Social services can improve the quality of health care services provided in primary health care. And the same time helping patients to get improved access to health care services through counseling and financial aid. Social services also have a role in improving the awareness of family members of patients' conditions and determinants. Social services in PHCs realize the social responsibility of primary health care services towards the families of patients in the community.

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